

Prospects to increase cropping intensity and production in 5-month irrigation areas

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In the 5-month irrigation areas of Indonesia, rains begin in September and land preparation for upland crops usually begins in October. But farmers cannot prepare the land for lowland rice culture until enough rain has fallen to soften the soil or until irrigation water comes in December. When water needs are met, the farmers prepare the seedbeds and begin to transplant about 30 to 40 days later. Pelita I/1 is harvested from 135 to 140 days after seedbed preparation or from mid-April to May. In May the irrigation water stops and the dry season begins. During this period about 90% of the rice land lies fallow. That area might

Average grain yield and income for superimposed study in 5-month irrigation areas. Cropping systems research, Nambahdadi, Lampung, Indonesia, 1975-76.

Cropping pattern	Yield (t/ha)			Income ^a (US\$/ha)			Total gross income (US\$/ha)
	1st crop	2nd crop	3rd crop	1st crop	2nd crop	3rd crop	
PelitaCorn-Rice bean	4.9	0.7	0.1	707	66	35	808
IR28-IR29-Mung beans	4.0	2.4	1.1	517	352	533	1,462
IR28-Sorghum-ratoon	3.6	2.4	-	525	88	-	613
IR28-Soybean-Mung beans	4.0	0.8	1.1	514	220	552	1,346
IR28-Peanut-Mung beans	4.3	0.3	1.0	625	158	449	1,232
IR28-Corn-Mung beans	4.0	2.1	1.2	511	198	597	1,372

^aPrices of crops determined at the conversion rate of Rp415 = US\$1.

be made more productive if farmers would plant a short-duration rice early in the rainy season, as soon as the irrigation water arrives or earlier. If IR28 were planted in November, it could be harvested 100 to 115 days later, in March or early April. After the harvest, there would still be enough water from rainfall and residual soil moisture to grow crops for 1 or 2 months. This concept was tested with six cropping patterns.

Two crops of early maturing rice

grown in the 5-month irrigation areas gave higher yields and gross returns than a single crop of the medium-maturing Pelita I/1 (see table).

A third crop of mung beans planted early in the rainy season, before the irrigation water arrives, can be productive and profitable. However, mung can be more logically considered as the first crop in the yearly sequence, as farmers consider it now in areas where upland crops are grown.

C171-136 upland rice compared with Dagge in a rice-corn cropping system in the Philippines

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For years, cropping systems researchers have attempted to find an upland rice variety better than the present one, Dagge, in an upland-rice site in Cale, Batangas province, Philippines. Until 1976 all varieties tested in farmers' fields failed, often because they could not withstand farmers' weeding practices, which involve passing a spike-toothed harrow, or *kalmot*, diagonally across the rows at from 10 to 20 days after emergence, followed by one or two interrow cultivations with a *lithao* (wooden furrow) and repeated hand weeding. The *kalmot* usually uprooted improved upland varieties. Furthermore, their shorter plant type often intensified weed problems later in the growing season, increasing labor requirements.

Dagge is harvested by removing individual panicles or cutting the entire

Weekly labor utilization and imputed weekly wage rates on 36 farms in Cale, Batangas province, Philippines, 1915-76.